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The Source and Establishment of the Image Style of Jiyue People in Longmen Grottoes during the Tang Dynasty

Guo Ziyuan

Abstract

As a special kind of Buddhist Jiyue theme, the images of Jiyue people (伎樂人) in the Longmen Grottoes during the Tang Dynasty are mainly composed of maiko (舞伎), musicians (樂伎) and geisha (歌伎) who show secular life. Influenced by the art of the Indian grottoes, the original images of Jiyue people were mostly in standing postures and were arranged in the stories of Buddha's life (佛本生) and Buddha's biography (佛傳故事), appearing as an integral part of expressing and conveying Buddhist scriptures with the function of setting off the main plot. In the Northern Dynasties, as a new form, the image of the wall-based Jiyue people (壁基伎樂人) was separated from the Buddhist story and gradually turned to secularization, mainly sitting, but only in the images of musicians. On the basis of inheriting the wall-based musicians of the Northern Dynasties, the new maiko and geisha appeared in the Longmen Grottoes. This new form, on the one hand, was deeply influenced by the Tang Dynasty palace music and dance culture, and it formed a mode of band composed of maiko, musicians, and geisha. On the other hand, the richness of the temple music and dance scenes and the temple musicians (寺屬音聲人) also had a greater or lesser impact on the images of the Jiyue people.

Key Words

Longmen Grottoes, Tang Dynasty, image of Jiyue people, Sitting Section Kabuki (坐部伎樂)

The Buddhist art of Longmen Grottoes, with statues as the carrier, had been greatly developed in the Tang Dynasty, the golden period of Chinese Buddhist art. In addition to the image of Acting Bodhisattva (伎樂天) on the top of the grottoes, the images of Jiyue people (伎樂人) carved at the bottom of the grottoes is one of the typical features of Buddhist art in Longmen Grottoes during the Tang Dynasty. Ru Zishen (孺子莘) pointed out that on the basis of the Central Plains culture, Buddhism in the Central Plains gradually formed in the process of collision and fusion with Indian Buddhism and Buddhism in the Western regions. From the early Eastern Han Dynasty into the Central Plains to the full maturity of the Sui and Tang dynasties, Han Buddhism was believed and respected by all classes.¹ Therefore, the historical process of the evolution of Buddhist art forms and styles can be seen in the art of the grottoes, and the dynamic process of its source and development can also

be seen in the style of the images of the Jiyue People. This paper intends to sort out the source and development of the image of Jiyue people, analyze the transformation of the image style of Jiyue people, and speculate on the factors behind the establishment of the image of Jiyue people in Longmen Grottoes during the Tang Dynasty.

1. From the Buddhist Context to the Secular Scene

The appearance of maiko (舞伎) and musicians (樂伎) together in images of Jiyue people can be traced as far back as the stone carvings of the Great Stupa of Balhut (巴爾胡特大塔) and the Great Stupa of Sanchi (桑奇大塔) in India. The relief on the outside of the lower level of the stone pillar at the south gate of the Balhut stupa shows a band of eight on the left side, five of whom are holding musical instruments, while the remaining three are either facing each other's backs or with their hands

intertwined. Their braided hair is draped behind their heads, and they are all in a seated position; on the right, there are four standing maiko with headscarves tied around their heads, one arm resting on their faces and the other outstretched. The necks of the musicians and maiko are wearing layers of collars, wrist bracelets, and their waists are tied with a woven pashmina, showing a strong Indian style. There is also a small child under the feet of the dancer. Liu Xinru (劉欣如) believes that the child under the feet of the dancer represents the newly born Buddha, and the overall picture shows the scene celebrating the birth of Buddha with music and dance (figure 1 A).²

The Jiyue people preserved on the front of the west pillar of the north gate of the Great Pagoda of Sanchi are shown together with the stupa and the two-winged Acting Bodhisattva. The stupa at the center of the picture serves to divide the Acting Bodhisattva from the Jiyue people and at the same time the stupa is a symbol of Buddha's nirvana, and the Acting Bodhisattva and Jiyue people surround the stupa to show their offerings to nirvana as a theme (figure 1 B).

At the beginning of the spread of Buddhism to the East, people's knowledge of Buddhism was in its infancy,

and it was still necessary to recognize and interpret Buddhist doctrine through the preaching of missionaries and Buddhist art.³ Therefore, manifested in the images of Jiyue people, they also mostly appear intertwined with the stories of Buddhist preaching and sutra changes.

The Yungang Grottoes (雲岡石窟) excavated in the Northern Wei Dynasty⁴ and the Jiyue people mainly appear in Buddhist stories. The sixth cave is the center of the tower pillar cave. In this cave the center pillar of the west and north of the lower level, respectively, are carved with "return to the city on the elephant (乘象歸城)" (figure 2 A) and "the crown prince back to the palace (太子回宮)" picture; both feature images of musicians playing the flute and the curved neck lute. In the same cave, in the lower part of the south wall of the main room, there is a portrait of Yasudhara (耶蘇陀羅摩訶夫人) "Surprised by Three Dreams (驚見三夢)" (figure 2 B), which depicts the crown prince preparing to become a Buddhist monk and Yasudhara in deep sleep. Below them, there are musicians with panpipes, drums, and wicker, but they are not playing.⁵ The thirty-eighth cave is the room on the north wall of the niche to the east side of the carving of the "Sakyamuni Nirvana

Figure 1 (A). South Gate of the Great Pagoda of Balhut; (B) West column of the north gate of the Great Pagoda of Sanchi. From Chen Xiaolu. *The Influence of Hellenization on Buddhist Fine Arts from the Images of Kabuki Feeders*.

Figure 2 (A). Cave 6 Prince Returning to the Palace on an Elephant; (B) Cave 6, Yashodhara, surprised by the three dreams; (C) Cave 38, the block inverted kabuki music. From the General Editorial Department of *Chinese Musical Relics*, ed. *Chinese music and cultural relics-Shanxi volume*.

Statue (釋迦涅槃像),” divided into three layers; Jiyue people are located in the bottom layer. Kabuki hold pipa, transverse flute, wicker bamboos, thin waist drums, round waist drums, panpipes, and other musical instruments for blowing and playing. In the same cave, there is also a lower layer of the north wall of the “block inverted kabuki (幢倒伎樂)” (figure 2 C), which is called “block inverted kabuki” or “block inverted music god” in the Buddhist scriptures. Meanwhile, block-down play is also a pole-climbing activity in hundreds of plays in ancient China, which appeared in the Qin and Han dynasties and was known as “searching for.” According to Gao Cheng’s *Shu Wu Ji Yuan* (《事物紀原》) of the Northern Song Dynasty, “Acrobatics originated in the Qin and Han Dynasties, mainly acrobatics, such as walking ropes, swallowing knives, stepping on fire barefoot, climbing poles, etc.”⁶ Yungang Grottoes in the “block down kabuki” is likely to be in India on the basis of Jiyue people, the integration of China’s Qin and Han period of folk theater activities, and the formation of a kind of Chinese Jiyue people image.

In summary, it can be seen in the Jiyue people images of the Yungang period that there is mostly a standing posture, with the Buddha’s life and the story of the Buddha as a performance that conveys the teachings of the sutra as part of the emergence of the function of the main plot. However, it should also be seen that at this time the block inverted kabuki also shows the side of secular life, indicating that the Jiyue people images have tended to gradually shift from the Buddhist context to secular life. As Mader (馬德) mentioned, from the moment

Buddhist art entered the Central Plains, the artistic characteristics of the two cultures began to merge. The initial fusion was a simple interspersion, and when Chinese culture penetrated Buddhist art the first thing seen was the transformation of cave architecture, figures and costumes, and painting techniques into the art of the Central Plains,⁷ manifested in the images of Jiyue people, i.e., the scenes in which the images existed, the stylistic features of the images, and the transformation of their nature.

2. Establishment of the Wall-base Jiyue People Image

With the collision and fusion of Buddhism and the culture of the Central Plains, the group of people who came to open caves, make statues, and offer offerings to the Buddha continued to expand. In addition to the monks, some kings and grandchildren, noblemen, and commoners were involved in the activities of opening caves and making statues. This brought about changes in thought, aesthetics, and emotion. In the fifth and sixth centuries, Buddhist images in China also entered a period of transition, with the earlier popular images of the Buddha’s life and the Buddha’s biography gradually disappearing.⁸ Jiyue people images also gradually turned to secularization from their initial role as a component of expressing and conveying the teachings of the Buddhist scriptures, detaching themselves from the stories of Buddhist biographies to exist independently in a seated position.

The Gongxian Grottoes (鞏縣石窟), which were open-

Figure 3 (A). West wall of the first cave of Gongxian Grottoes; (B) West wall of the third cave; (C) West wall of the fourth cave. From Henan Provincial Institute of Cultural Relics, ed. *Caves of China-Gongxian Cave Temple*.

Figure 4. The main wall of the second cave in the North Xiangtangshan Grottoes. From Chinese Art Complete Collection Editorial Committee ed. *Chinese Fine Arts Complete Works 35 Sculpture Editions Sculptures of Anyang Grottoes in Xiangtangshan, Tianlong Mountain, Gong County*.

Figure 5 (A). The front of the center column of Cave 45; (B) The front of the center column of Cave 46 in Xumishan. From The Cultural Relics Management Committee of Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, edited by the Department of Art History of the Central Academy of Fine Arts, *Xumishan Grottoes*.

ed during the period from Shen Gui to Xiao Chang (518-528 CE), were the latest grottoes built by the Northern Wei Dynasty. Compared with the Longmen Grottoes, the carvings are richer in subject matter, with the addition of images of Jiyue supporters, earth deities (地神), and exotic animals (異獸), in addition to God-King. Jiyue people in Gongxian Grottoes (figure 3) appear at the base of the walls of the first, third and fourth caves, all in a seated position. The Jiyue people are either wearing small lotus-shaped crowns or domed crowns, either bare or wearing long open-necked garments, with wide hakama or narrow pants and silk draping behind them. The same kind of images of Jiyue people also appeared in the Xiangtangshan Grottoes (響堂山石窟) and the Xumishan Grottoes (須彌山石窟). The Xiangtangshan Grottoes include the South Xiangtang, North Xiangtang,

and Xiao Xiangtang, and the images of Jiyue people are carved at the base of the altars in the fifth grotto of the South Xiangtang and the second grotto of the North Xiangtang Mountain (figure 4). The Jiyue figures are all seated, with their scarves flowing behind them. The forty-fifth and forty-sixth caves of the Xumishan Grottoes are both center-pillar caves, and each of the four sides of the center pillar is open to a niche. Jiyue people images were distributed in the center column four niches under the seat of the face and the south side of the niche under the seat of the face (figure 5), kneeling, wearing round neck and narrow-sleeved Hu clothing.

There is also a statue of the Liu's Family Thinking Bodhisattva Statue (劉氏家族思維菩薩像) at the site of Xiude Temple in Quyang, Hebei Province (河北曲陽修德寺遺址), in the eighth year of Tianbao of the Northern

Qi Dynasty (557 CE). The front, left and right sides of the base of the statue are divided into three layers, the upper layer on the left and right sides is carved with a niche for the Buddha and two supporters; the lower layer is carved with a statue of the god and king; and the middle layer is carved with images of four Jiyue people (figure 6). The Jiyue people are all seated, with double buns and bare upper bodies. From left to right, the Jiyue people on the right side are holding panpipes, beating capricorn drums, clapping waist drums, and playing flutes; and on the left side, they are holding panpipes, playing dongxiao (cave flutes), holding sheng, and playing pipas.⁹

The layout and structure of Jiyue people images on the pedestals of the Gongxian Grottoes, the Xiangtangshan Grottoes, the Xumishan Grottoes, and the Liu's Family Thinking Bodhisattva Statue are similar, being on the lower part of the wall, with no maiko and geisha (歌伎), only one type of musicians, and grouped together with statues of the god and king, statues of exotic beasts, Boshan Censer and lions, etc. The overall narrative color is weakened compared to the previous ones, which were used to set up the plot of Buddhist stories. Compared to the Jiyue people previously used as plot elements in Buddhist stories, the overall narrative is weakened, and more emphasis is placed on the Jiyue people representing secular offerings. This kind of Jiyue people in a seated position at the base of the wall gradually developed into a fixed form and appeared in the Tang Dynasty caves of the Longmen Grottoes.

3. Tang Dynasty Sitting Section Kabuki and Longmen Grottoes Jiyue People

In the Longmen Grottoes, Tang Dynasty Jiyue people vary in number: there are five body, six body, eight body, ten body, twelve body five, to twelve body most; all are carved at the base of the wall, in the maiko, musicians and geisha composition. Maiko is in the center of the wall, symmetrical, and musicians and geisha are in Maiko on both sides, mostly in the front or three-quarters of the side.¹⁰

Through the Longmen Grottoes Tang Dynasty Jiyue people image style combing can be found from Gongxian Grottoes to the Longmen Grottoes, in addition to the increase of the maiko and geisha, as well as the Jiyue people posture, holding a musical instrument in some changes in the details of the overall style of sitting remain unchanged, In addition, the Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images show the music and dance scenes and style features of the Tang Dynasty and the sitting part of the kabuki have some relevance.

According to the *Old Record of the Tang Dynasty* (*Jiu Tang Shu*, 《舊唐書》), at the beginning of the Tang Dynasty, the court music and dance began to set up the two parts of standing and sitting. "After Gao Zu ascended the throne, banquet performances were based on the old system of the Sui Dynasty, using Court Music (Jiubuyue, 九部樂), which was then divided into two parts, standing and sitting."¹¹ *Tong Dian* (《通典》) records: "In the early

Figure 6. Liu's Family Thinking Bodhisattva Statue Pedestal (right side and left side). From Hu Guoqiang, *The Liu Family Made the Thinking Statue Date and Related to the North Dynasty Thinking Statue Problem*.

days of Wu De (武德)...according to the old system of the Sui dynasty, playing Court Music. To the Tang Dynasty Zhen Guan sixteen years in November... increased to Shibuji (十部伎), then divided into two parts of the standing sitting. Standing Kabuki has eight...Sitting Section Kabuki has six...”¹² It shows that in the period of Gao Zong (高宗), there were already two classifications of Kabuki music. *New Record of the Tang Dynasty* (Xin Tang Shu, 《新唐書》) records: “(Xuan Zong) It was divided into Erbuji (二部伎), Standing and playing under the hall are called Standing Kabuki, and sitting in the hall and playing is Sitting Section Kabuki.”¹³ As seen in the Xuan Zong period, and according to the performance form of the orchestra while sitting, two parts of the kabuki were subdivided. Among them, the “Tang Shang (堂上)” is the Sitting Section Kabuki (坐部伎), which refers to the performance indoors or in the hall. The number of seated kabuki was small, but the musicians were of high caliber and had a wide variety of instruments, as mentioned in Bai Juyi’s poem “Standing Kabuki (立部伎).”

Sorting through the six kabuki of the Sitting Section Kabuki, it can be seen that the first *Yan Yue* (《燕樂》) is composed of four small musical dances with diverse and colorful costumes. The instruments used in the *Yan Yue* are recorded in the *Tong Dian* as follows: “One jade chime, one large square rattle, one flute and zither, one building, one reclining konghou (箜篌), one large konghou, one small konghou, one large pipa (琵琶), one small pipa, one large five-stringed pipa, one small five-stringed pipa, one blowing leaf, one large sheng (笙), one small sheng, one large wickerwork (箎), one small wickerwork, one large xiao (簫), one small xiao, one copper cymbal (銅鈸), one long flute, one shakuhachi, one piccolo, one wiped out drum, one continuous drum, one drum with a rattle, two Tao (鞀) drums, two drums with floating drums, and two songs.”¹⁴ Of the remaining five, the Longchi music (龍池樂) uses Ya music (雅樂), and the remaining four use Qiuci music (龜茲樂). As Li Baojie (李寶傑) mentioned, the configuration of the instruments of the Saito Kabuki orchestra was not fixed, but changed according to the requirements of the specific works, which showed the characteristics of “flexible and free orchestra combinations.”¹⁵ The instruments used by the Qiuci music, according to the *Tong Dian*, records: “Qiuci music...dance four people...music with vertical konghou one, pipa one, five-stringed pipa one, sheng one, transverse flute one, xiao one, wickerwork one, Dara drums one, waist drums one, capricorn (羯) drums one, Maoyan (毛員) drums one (original note: now dead), Jilou (雞婁) drums one, copper cymbals two,

shells one.”¹⁶

Comparing the records of musical instruments used in the literature, such as zheng (箏), pipa, sheng, wicker bamboos, transverse flutes, waist drums, vertical konghou, copper cymbals, Jilou drums, etc., all appeared in the images of Jiyue people in the Longmen Grottoes, but only in a slightly different number from the documentary records.

This situation also occurs in Tang Dynasty tomb murals. The earliest appearance of images of Jiyue figures in Tang tomb murals was in the tomb of Li Shou, King Jing of Huai’an, in the fifth year of the Zhen Guan reign (631 CE), unearthed in Shaanxi in 1973. It is worth noting that the inner wall of the stone coffin has line carvings of kabuki, with six maiko on the west wall of the coffin, twelve Sitting Section Musicians (坐部樂伎) on the north wall (figures 7, 8), and twelve Standing Musicians (立部樂伎) on the east wall, all divided into three rows. The Sitting Section Musicians are all wearing narrow-sleeved topcoats, long skirts and scarves. They are holding vertical konghou, straight-necked pipa, curved-necked pipa, zheng, sheng, transverse flute, panpipe, wickerwork, cymbals, dala drums, waist drums, and shells. They are sitting and playing with waist drums and shells.¹⁷ We know that the tomb murals of the Han and Wei dynasties have been, to a certain extent, a reproduction of the tomb owner’s life and a yearning for the world after death, with a certain degree of realism and imagination. Li Xingming (李星明) also mentioned that the music and dance pictures in the tomb murals are not only the simulation of the enjoyment scene of the royal nobles, but also the service to the world after the death of the tomb owner, so their secular meanings will be extended and transformed to a certain extent.¹⁸ Looking closely at the images of kabuki on the line-carved murals of Li Shou’s tomb, the configurations and numbers of musical instruments do not correspond one by one with the literature while showing the condition of the tomb owner during his lifetime. This is due to the fact that, on the one hand, the Sitting Section of Kabuki belonged to the Tang Dynasty court music and dance, and the orchestra arrangement would be made according to different occasions in line with the requirements of etiquette. On the other hand, as a special spatial place, the mural paintings in the tomb are often limited by its layout or the number of characters. Therefore, the mural paintings of Li Shou’s tomb cannot directly correspond to the scenes of Tang court music, but is only to a certain extent a depiction of Tang Dynasty sitting and standing kabuki.¹⁹

By going back to the Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images from the Tang Dynasty, you can understand why

Figure 7. Sitting Section Kabuki diagram of Li Shou's tomb. From *The Excavation Bulletin of Li Shou's Tomb in Tang Dynasty*.

Figure 8. The line-engraved diagram of Sitting Section Kabuki. From Sun Ji, *Tang Li Shou Stone Coffin Line Engraving "maid figure" and "music and dance figure" Scattered Notes* (below).

the number of Jiyue people images and the use of musical instruments and literature have a slight discrepancy. This is due to the fact that the carving of kabuki in the grottoes needed to be carried out according to the size and layout of the grottoes, the requirements of the donor to fund the opening of the grottoes, etc.²⁰ Thus, there are changes in the music and dance scale, instrument types, or increases and decreases. Secondly, the Jiyue people images in the grottoes represent virtual music and dance scenes, which have a certain distance from real life. The Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images from the Tang Dynasty and Tang Li Shou tomb of the sitting part of the Kabuki music, although they show the same form of the sitting part of the kabuki, cannot be thought of as a real portrayal of the use of music, and it cannot be completely associated with the specific mode of band it corresponds to. As Gong Dazhong (宮大中) mentioned, it was sculpted with reference to the Sitting Section Kabuki from the early Tang Dynasty onward.²¹

In addition, there is another issue to consider. At that time, there were also more scenes of music and dance performances and musicians in the monasteries, and there is the question of whether the images of Jiyue people in the Longmen Grottoes were also influenced by them.

First of all, during the Northern Wei Dynasty in the temple the music, dance and theater activities were extremely rich, according to *The Record of Buddhist Temples in Luoyang* (《洛陽伽藍記》) in the relevant records. Afterwards, the Buddhist customs that prevailed in the Northern Wei Dynasty, such as some religious music and dance activities in the monasteries, were inherited and maintained in the Tang Dynasty. The *Luoyang Canon* (《洛陽大典》) records: "Wu Zetian and Gao Zong moved the capital to Luoyang, excavated the Longmen Grottoes, Touring Songshan Mountain, and built the Longevity god palace. On the 21st day of the first month of the year 680 (the second year of the Tiao Lu year), Wu Zetian personally hosted a banquet for the

ministers in the south city of Luoyang, inviting them to watch songs and dance dramas.”²² *Nan Bu Xin Shu* (《南史》) recorded: “Most of the theaters in Chang’an were concentrated in Ci’en Temple, Qinglong Temple, followed by Jianfu Temple and Yongshou Temple.”²³ But is it the monks and nuns or the musicians who perform in the theater and the singing field of the monastery?

Tang Liu Dian (《唐六典》) contains: “All Taoist priests, female Taoist, monks, monks and nuns... performing music and drama, are required to do hard labor.”²⁴ Jiang Boqin (薑伯勤) has examined the Dunhuang temple musicians: “According to the Tang dynasty law and orthodox internal law, monks are forbidden to perform, so the music furnishings in the temple must be made with the help of the temple musicians.”²⁵ Xiang Yang (項陽) also pointed out that from the Northern and Southern dynasties to the Sui and Tang dynasties, most people who played music in the monasteries were temple musicians or specially invited kabuki, not real monks.²⁶ It can be seen that monks and nuns could not engage in musical performance, and those who performed were mostly the people who were trained by the monasteries to set up music and performances as a profession. Zhang Zhentao (張振濤) mentioned in his research that the research results of Dunhuang documents show that there are a large number of art monks in Dunhuang monasteries. The images of kabuki flying skies depicted in Dunhuang frescoes are all from the monasteries. They are reproductions of the scenes in the monasteries rather than visions of the heavenly realm.²⁷ From this association, carved in the Longmen Grottoes at the base of the wall of the Jiyue people, is it also a reproduction of the temple music and dance scene? If so, then the kabuki who performed and offered music in the temple could also be a reference to the images of Jiyue people in the Longmen Grottoes.

To summarize, the sitting and standing divisions already existed in the period of Gaozong and the sitting and standing divisions of kabuki were fully established in the period of Xuanzong, according to the relevant articles on the Longmen Grottoes, and can be seen in the staging.²⁸ The images of Jiyue people in the Longmen Grottoes also appeared centrally in this period. At the end of Emperor Xuanzong’s reign, the An-Shi Rebellion (安史之亂) broke out, An Lushan captured Chang’an and Luoyang, and the Tang Dynasty went from strength to strength. In this context, the palace music and dance organizations were gradually reduced, and the number of court entertainers was also reduced. *Later Tang Dynasty* contains: “Leap month of the 14th year of the Dali (大曆) calendar...close the pear garden, the remaining three

hundred people belonged to Taichang Temple.”²⁹ In the same situation, there are also the sound people of the temple. During the reign of Emperor Xuanzong, Tang Xuanzong was supportive of Buddhism, but in the face of its overdevelopment, he enacted a series of restrictive policies. In the case of the monasteries, the *Book of the Whole Tang Dynasty* (*Quan Tang Wen*, 《全唐文》) records: “All the temples and monasteries in the world...From now on, no new temples can be built...”³⁰ Once the edict forbidding the creation of temples was issued, to some extent, it had a repressive effect on the development of monasteries. During the reign of Emperor Wu of the Tang Dynasty, they prohibited the people from providing Buddha statues and ordered the ban on the destruction of the world’s Buddhist temples: “In the fifth year of Hui Chang (會昌, 845 CE), ...therefore more than four thousand six hundred monasteries were demolished, and two hundred and sixty-five thousand monks and nuns were returned to secularism...”³¹ With the decline of the temples, the temple musicians were also lost. Correspondingly, the images of Jiyue people have not appeared in the Longmen Grottoes since then.

Through the above analysis, combined with the Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images of the Tang Dynasty appearing and disappearing over time, the Tang Dynasty Sitting Section Kabuki and the temple musicians of the time, and using the prevalence and decline of the people for comparison, it can be speculated that the Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images were, in the inheritance of the wall-based Jiyue people, on the one hand deeply affected by the Tang Dynasty court music and dance culture, and the formation of the orchestra mode of maiko, musicians and geisha combination. On the other hand, the rich temple music and dance scenes, as well as the temple musicians, also influenced the Jiyue people images to a greater or lesser extent, or in other words, the images can be seen as part of the appearance of the temple musicians in the Tang Dynasty.

Jiyue people images, as a part of cave statues, first appeared in Indian Buddhist stories, as part of the expression and communication of the teachings of the Buddhist scriptures. Between the fifth and sixth centuries, the images of Jiyue people in the Yungang Grottoes entered into a period of transition, and the initial popularity of the images of the Buddha’s birth and the Buddha’s biography gradually faded away.³² The Jiyue people in the grottoes in the Northern Dynasty period only had musicians, and the maiko and geisha appeared in the Tang Dynasty caves of the Longmen Grottoes. There are three ways to form and establish

the images of Jiyue people in Longmen Grottoes during the Tang Dynasty. First, the maiko and musicians in the great tower of Balhut, India; although both are in a standing position, to a certain extent they provide similar scenes for the images of Jiyue people. Second, Gongxian Grottoes and other Jiyue people images of that location, as well as the posture of the Jiyue people, for the Longmen Grottoes Jiyue people images of the Tang Dynasty show the formation of a fixed program that laid the foundation. Finally, the images of Jiyue people were influenced by the Tang Dynasty Sitting Section Kabuki, and gradually formed a relatively fixed orchestra combination of maiko, musicians and geisha. In addition, according to the literature on the Tang Dynasty temple theater, song field records, and through the kabuki parti-

cipation and creation of music and dance scenes, it is speculated that Jiyue people images may also have a certain relationship with the temple musicians.

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龍門石窟唐代伎樂人圖像樣式的來源與確立

郭子源

摘要：龍門石窟唐代伎樂人圖像作為佛教伎樂題材中特殊的一種，以表現世俗生活的舞伎、樂伎與歌伎為主要內容。伎樂人圖像受到印度石窟藝術的影響，最初的伎樂人圖像多為站姿，被安排在佛本生、佛傳故事中，作為表現和傳達佛經教義的組成部分出現，具有烘托主要情節的功能。北朝時期，壁基伎樂人圖像作為一種新的形式從佛傳故事中脫離出來，逐漸轉向世俗化，以坐姿為主，但僅有樂伎的形象。龍門石窟的伎樂人圖像在繼承北朝壁基樂伎的基礎之上，新出現舞伎和歌伎。這種新的形式，一方面，深受唐代宮廷樂舞文化的影響，形成了舞伎、樂伎和歌伎組合而成的樂隊模式；另一方面，當時豐富的寺院樂舞場景以及寺屬音聲人也對伎樂人圖像產生或多或少的影響。

關鍵詞：龍門石窟；唐代；伎樂人圖像；坐部伎樂